

Application notes protocol (expert-based assessment)

This document replaces the workshop observation format with a record consistent with the paper's evaluation: two experts apply the method independently. The goal is to capture findings, frictions, and traceability evidence.

1. Metadata

Field	Value
Date	2026-02-05
Mode	Individual (asynchronous) application + artifact review
Participants	E1, E2 (external experts, 5+ years)
System	Academic information system (SOA) with sensitive data
ASRs covered	ASR_1, ASR_2, ASR_3

2. Dimensions to observe

- D1 - Understanding of the method: clarity of steps, inputs/outputs.
- D2 - Scenario quality: template completeness, verifiable measures, lack of ambiguity.
- D3 - Traceability: ability to connect ASR → QA → ZT → mechanisms → scenarios.
- D4 - Perceived effort: time/iteration required to refine SIGs and scenarios.
- D5 - Decision value: whether the artifacts help justify architectural decisions.

3. Application notes (structured summary)

Step	Observation (synthesis)
Identify QA	Both experts mapped ASR_1 to Confidentiality (primary) and Integrity (secondary), ASR_2 to Auditability, and ASR_3 to Availability.
Build SIGs	Explicitly introducing ZT principles as intermediate nodes helped justify mechanisms and avoid ad-hoc selections. It was recommended to document why a mechanism contributes (or not) to a specific QA.
Map to QAS	Scenarios became more analyzable by requiring a response measure. It was recommended to refine measures so they can be verified through testing or monitoring (e.g., windows, thresholds, and criteria).

4. Typical frictions and mitigations

Friction	Impact	Proposed mitigation
Ambiguity in "detection window" (SA_1)	Hard to operationalize the response measure	Define a threshold (e.g., minutes) consistent with monitoring capabilities and system criticality.

Policy granularity (A13) and attributes (A16)	May increase complexity	Start with a minimal subset of attributes and policies; expand iteratively with case evidence.
Choosing mechanisms per principle	Risk of missing alternatives	Keep a short list of mechanisms per principle and justify selection in the SIG (explicit traceability).

5. Quotes (anonymized)

- “The SIG makes the reasoning chain between ASR and mechanism explicit; it helps justify decisions.”
- “The biggest value is in forcing scenarios with measures; without a response measure, the discussion becomes vague.”

6. Closing

Operational conclusion: the expert-based assessment suggests the method improves traceability and structures the derivation of ZT scenarios from ASRs. Using SIGs helps make contributions and trade-offs explicit, and the QAS template forces the definition of responses and verifiable measures.